

Workshop: West Asia in the Centre

Decolonizing orientalist narratives of the past and present

23rd of May 2023 | Room 22.0.49 | 9:00 – 17:00

Programme

Timeslot	Speaker(s)	Title
9:00-9:30	<i>Chairs of the workshop</i>	Introduction into the theme
9:30-10:00	Tolin Jojo/Yvonne Helmholtz	„Objects of highly scientific interest“
10:00-10:30	Rune Rattenborg	Collateral Colonialism: Etymologies of Space and the Chance Creation of the 'Land Between the Rivers'
10:30-11:00	Zahra Kouzehgari	Ernest Herzfeld and 'Decolonizing' Archaeological Studies in Iran. A Look through the Documents in The National Library and Archives of Iran
11:00-11:30	Coffee Break	
11:30-12:00	Noemi Schürmann	A Glimpse of the Orient: The 19th century image of Orientalism in the Basel journal "Das Morgenland. Altes und Neues für Freunde der heiligen Schrift" (1838-1843)
12:00-12:30	Heidi J. Miller	Unchanging India and the Indus Civilization (c. 2600-1900 BC); Deconstructing the Orientalist Idea of Homogeneity through Time and Space
12:30-13:00	Eric X. Jarrard	A Necrographic Case Study: The Wellesley Neo-Assyrian Relief
13:00-14:00	Lunch	
14:00-14:30	Luise Loges	Framing Looted Heritage: How news media and collectors use orientalist narratives in the discourse of antiquities looting and trafficking
14:30-15:00	Barbara Banasik	Decolonizing museum practices - case study of the exhibition "Museum? What for?"
15:00-15:30	Sebastian Hageneuer	Playing Archaeology, Playing Colonialism
15:30-16:00	Coffee Break	
16:00-16:30	Bärbel Morstadt	Historising Epidemais – West Asian characters in the comic series 'Asterix the Gaul' against the background of historical sources, the 20th-century-Zeitgeist and the current discourse on orientalism
16:30-17:00	<i>All participants</i>	Closing discussion

Abstracts

Part 1: Orientalism in the disciplines of the past

Tolin Jojo/Yvonne Helmholtz (Freie Universität Berlin) | 9:30-10:00

„Objects of highly scientific interest“

According to their labour contract, the engineers who worked for the construction of the Baghdad and Hejaz railway in the 20th century had to record the find of cultural assets that could be of highly scientific value. The declaration of such findings had to be made to the Bagdadbahn-Gesellschaft, an international association that gave most of the financial backing to support the project during the time of the Ottoman Empire. Companies like the Deutsche Bank became part of this group. Not only the pecuniary resources circulated partly from the German area, but also the technical support and the building materials such as rails were exported services and products from that region. As a result, we recognize several German companies which got involved in the installation of that railway network. One of the most influential companies was the Philipp Holzmann AG that managed the construction of railway stations, bridges, tunnels, and repositories for the building materials and therefore hired professional engineers. As a legacy, the archive of this concern stored hundreds of photographs and documents as contemporary witnesses. These documents demonstrate and illustrate all the circumstances concerning this enormous project of the 20th century in West Asia.

This paper attempts to shed light on the passages that introduce this summary: Where are the objects of highly scientific interest today? Who got involved? Who received these cultural assets? The above-mentioned Philipp Holzmann AG archive will serve as the basis for answering the raised questions.

Rune Rattenborg (Uppsala University) | 10:00-10:30

Collateral Colonialism: Etymologies of Space and the Chance Creation of the ‘Land Between the Rivers’

Vocabularies of space define the world. Yet, despite their apparent conceptual authority, lineages of cartographic entities are often blurred, accidental, and produced from etymologies only imperfectly understood by their translators. Drawing on a recent study on past and present meanings of the term ‘Mesopotamia’, this paper reviews the inadvertent, if now institutionalised separation of modern and historical geographies of the state of ‘Iraq in Western - and global - discourse. Though widely conceived of as a textbook example of colonialist discursive dispossession of a nation’s heritage, this paper further explores the basic argument that ‘Mesopotamia’ - in the sense that we understand it today - is an unintended by-product of British military nomenclature during the First World War. As such, ‘Mesopotamia’ is itself a freak accident of history, the vestige of a haphazard series of historical events far removed from the biographies attributed to it by contemporary Western society. This ironic state of affairs is reviewed through a discussion of its continued reaffirmation and widespread use in spatial discourses of archaeological and historical scholarship, arts trade and antiquities trafficking, and in popular media worldwide.

Zahra Kouzehgari (Université Lumière Lyon 2) | 10:30-11:00

Ernest Herzfeld and 'Decolonizing' Archaeological Studies in Iran. A Look through the Documents in The National Library and Archives of Iran

Archaeological studies in Iran date back a century and a half, starting with Nasir al-Din Shah Qajar's excavations in Khurhe near Tehran in 1859. During this period, there was an increasing interest in Iran's past among western travellers and high demand for its ancient objects in their museums. The arrival of the French in 1884 and their concession of archaeological excavations in Iran in 1895 made them the pioneers of continued archaeological studies in this region. The 18th of October 1927 abolishing all capitulatory privileges, including the French monopoly on archaeological excavation, significantly impacted Iranian archaeological studies. This event is considered a turning point in the history of these studies. It divides it before and after the 'abolition of French Monopoly.' From then on, the French expeditions were gradually limited to Susa, and the field was opened for the activities of delegations of other countries in various regions of Iran. A lot has been written about this transformation period. One of this era's most significant and efficient figures was Ernest Herzfeld, who played a crucial role. The present paper aims to study his role based on the surviving official documents in Iran's national library and archives. It includes his official and personal correspondence, as well as contracts. Further to information concerning Herzfeld's activities, these documents also provide valuable information concerning the French, German, and American archaeologists' rivalry to excavate binding sites in Iran.

Noemi Schürmann (University of Zürich) | 11:30-12:00

A Glimpse of the Orient: The 19th century image of Orientalism in the Basel journal "Das Morgenland. Altes und Neues für Freunde der heiligen Schrift" (1838-1843)

"We intend to acquaint our readers with the various peoples who at present inhabit the biblical lands, and to bring their customs and opinions, their habits and religious ideas, to the general knowledge."

This is what the Basel pastor Samuel Preiswerk (1799-1871) formulated as one of the motivations for the publication of his journal "Das Morgenland. Altes und Neues für Freunde der Heiligen Schrift" (trans. The Orient. Old and New for Friends of the Holy Scripture), which will be the main subject of my talk. The quotation gives an idea of how strong the interest in the land of the Bible was in the 19th century – in the wake of the emerging Oriental studies. Basel in particular had taken up the motto "Go and explore the land" and established missionary and scientific contacts with Palestine on the foundation of Oriental studies laid in the 18th century.

It is obvious that this increasing attention was also reflected in journals in Basel. This illustrates how tolerable these sources are as a reflection of religious, theological, political, and cultural imagination and can depict the representation of the "rediscovered Orient," especially the Holy Land in the 19th century.

My presentation will ask about the representation of Palestine drawn in the journal "Das Morgenland" and its perceptions, which are designed via text and image of the Holy Land. This should shed light on how these collective impressions and attributions were conveyed to the journal readership in theological circles in Basel in the mid-nineteenth century. It is precisely this cultural contact, which in the form of travellers' accounts of their experiences

was a prerequisite for the compilation of the journal, that calls into question the narrative of the Orient as the "cultural antithesis" to the West that has long been received in Orientalism research. In the course of this new research interest – which does not focus primarily on the foreignness of the Orient but seeks to trace the multi-layered discourse since the beginning of Oriental studies in the 18th century – this examination reveals the complex narrative structures between East and West. In doing so, it is important not to ignore the imagination of the "Oriental Other" against the background of power relations and hegemonic aspirations of the West, but to direct the microscopic view also to the syncretisms of the cultural spaces. The present analysis concentrates on these contact zones and consciously commits itself to a theory of Orientalism that does not proceed from a binary scheme of Occident versus Orient and the Orient as a purely Western construct.

The Basel source is intended to give empirical substance to this new approach to orientalism research. Orientalism and Oriental Studies sources are embedded in a considerable wealth of methodological and interdisciplinary approaches. I will approach this journal source from a historical-critical and religious studies perspective. It will become apparent that Basel theology in the 19th century certainly held a much more differentiated view of the Orient than long assumed.

Heidi J. Miller (Middlesex Community College, USA) | 12:00-12:30

Unchanging India and the Indus Civilization (c. 2600-1900 BC); Deconstructing the Orientalist Idea of Homogeneity through Time and Space

Orientalist histories of ancient South Asia focused primarily on ancient texts and the assumption of their absolute truths, and in turn this created a static view of the past. The idea of an unchanging India, of traditions encased within a living museum, has had an unacknowledged influence on archaeological excavation and interpretation in the Subcontinent. In this paper I will focus on one period, that of the Indus Civilization (c. 2600-1900 BC) and explore how this orientalist mantra of 'unchanging India' contributed to the idea of material culture homogeneity.

The archaeology of the Indus Civilization was first described and published by Sir John Marshall and for decades it was seen as unchanging and static over time and space. Within the 'twin capital' sites of Mohenjo-daro and Harappa, separated by approximately 700 kms, the material remains of each site's urban Harappan cultural phase were believed to be the same and homogeneous, over 700 years. This led to an interpretation of a controlling centralised political structure, managed by priest-kings. Archaeologists have pointed to early improper excavation techniques as the primary contributor to this homogeneity argument, yet the discovery and description of the Indus sites within a context of the orientalist 'unchanging India' paradigm has not been directly addressed. In order to properly understand the historiography of archaeology in the Subcontinent, the impact of orientalist discourse must be taken into account.

Part 2: Orientalism in heritage spaces

Eric X. Jarrard (Wellesley College) | 12:30-13:00

A Necrographic Case Study: The Wellesley Neo-Assyrian Relief

Over the last decade, Cameroonian philosopher Achille Mbembe has developed the concept of necropolitics as a biting critique of the Eurocentrism of Foucault's biopolitical discourse. For Mbembe, one must account for the damaging legacy of colonial histories to appreciate the effects of empire on the human body. Building on Mbembe, the art historian Dan Hicks has advanced the concept of necrography—or inverse history—as a productive paradigm by which the looted Benin Objects in the collection of the British Museum might be analysed as a legacy of colonial war. Such efforts, he contends, seek to examine what it means to study objects pillaged and plundered through the colonialist efforts of England. He suggests that a necrography of looted objects provides the desperately needed context that has been stripped away from them in the service of the colonial enterprise.

Using Hicks's work as a blueprint, this paper investigates a single object from a different time, place, and collection—the “Captive Being Flayed” or the so-called Wellesley Eunuch [Wellesley Davis Museum; 1883.1]. The Davis maintains sparse details—provenance, origin, the subject it depicts—concerning the 30 cm triangular piece of a Neo-Assyrian relief, which remains tucked away in its archives; those that are available are implausible when subjected to minimal scrutiny.

This paper provides a preliminary necrology for this object. In so doing, I attempt to answer the fundamental question: What is our responsibility to the objects in our care? And, more importantly, how the curation of these objects extends the orientalist impulses out of which they were procured, metastasizing into new lieux de memoire as satellites of decaying empires.

Luise Loges (University of Glasgow) | 14:00-14:30

Framing Looted Heritage: How news media and collectors use orientalist narratives in the discourse of antiquities looting and trafficking

Looting and trafficking of archaeological objects is a worldwide problem, which often becomes more severe during armed conflicts - two examples being the looting of Iraqi museums and archaeological sites after 2003, and the plundering of Syrian heritage during the civil war. The shock value of archaeological destruction often attracts international media attention - in fact, it has even been used as a means to draw attention to conflict-related loss of life. In some situations, the reporting of European news media on the obliteration of what is perceived as "world heritage" can support and even inspire public outrage among their audience. Yet the narratives used in these media are often steeped in orientalist stereotypes passed down from colonial times.

In my ongoing doctoral research, I discuss how the depiction of the market for ancient West Asian artefacts in German-language newspapers has shifted from a positive view on supposed "saviours" of ancient culture to a more sinister portrayal in light of conflict-related looting in Iraq and Syria. This change in representation has roused public concern and led to reactions by authorities, such as Germany's 2016 Cultural Heritage Protection Law. In turn, the antiquities market has reacted defensively to this portrayal, using the same already known orientalist tropes.

In my talk, I will use Germany as a case study to show how European news media and antiquities market actors frame the discourse on illicit Iraqi and Syrian heritage and discuss how orientalist narratives used by both sides exclude voices from source countries.

Barbara Banasik (Asia and Pacific Museum, Warsaw) | 14:30-15:00

Decolonizing museum practices - case study of the exhibition “Museum? What for?”

In November 2021 the Asia and Pacific Museum opened the new temporary exhibition entitled “Museum? What for?”, where we attempt to decolonize museum narratives, collecting strategies and exhibiting. The temporary exhibition “Museum? What for?” inquires about the things that are not there. Our historical narrative is governed by “lack”: the facts and people that were left out of it. We can fill in these gaps and develop alternative histories. What is missing from the museums we know?

Traces of the histories of Asian and Pacific cultures and their artefacts, which are not displayed alongside their European counterparts. The first part of the exhibition explores the history of modern museology in Europe. At this stage we also fill in the blanks in history. We place exhibits hailing from Asia and the Pacific region into “classical” museum displays. We rectify the “omissions”.

The exhibition encourages a change of perspective and seeing Europe as “the rest of the world” for once. It prompts reflection on one’s own history and attitude towards reality. In this paper I would like to present the strategies and narratives that we have chosen and their reception by a broader audience.

Exhibition website and catalogue (in Polish and English): wystawa.muzeumazji.pl

Part 3: Orientalism and Media and final discussion

Sebastian Hageneuer (University of Cologne) | 15:00-15:30

Playing Archaeology, Playing Colonialism

Modern video games depicting the past or the profession of Archaeology (in the widest sense) are more popular than ever. In addition to the fact that today the video game industry has more revenue than the film industry, every fourth successful video game depicts either the past itself or the profession of Archaeology in some way. Although commonly accepted that these video games do not adequately depict reality, certain stereotypes exist and prolong. While some depict adventure and exotic locations and therefore seem attractive, they (and many others) are based on colonialist tropes that are deeply rooted in Imperial Archaeology. Given the popularity of these games, colonialist tropes connected to our profession are communicated unfiltered to a wider audience.

In this chapter I present an abridged version of my dissertation in which I compare archaeological depictions of the 19th/20th century with the depiction of the past and the profession of Archaeology in modern-day video games. After establishing a theoretical background into media studies and the way video game players learn through video games, I want to analyse several games and their depiction of the past and our profession. I will show how colonialist tropes have survived through stereotypes and have established a colonial view on the past and the profession of Archaeology in video games. Given the popularity of these games especially with a younger audience, the relevance of this analysis becomes evident.

Bärbel Morstadt (Ruhr University, Bochum) | 16:00-16:30

Historising Epidemais – West Asian characters in the comic series ‘Asterix the Gaul’ against the background of historical sources, the 20th-century-Zeitgeist and the current discourse on orientalism

Asterix the Gaul is one of the most successful comic series in the world. In it, the writer René Goscinny and the illustrator Albert Uderzo depict the adventures of Asterix and his friends: Based in a small village in Gaul otherwise conquered by the Romans, they experience various adventures in the ancient Mediterranean world of the time around 50 BCE, and they meet various characters also from different West Asian cultures, among them the Phoenician merchant and seafarer Epidemais.

The first volume of the comic series was published in 1959 and since then, it enjoyed an impressive success: numerous other volumes appeared, they were translated into various languages, including even Latin, the stories were filmed as comics and with real actors. The characters in the comic series are loved by children of many generations, and the depictions are celebrated for their historical accuracy to such an extent that teachers, for example, use the volumes in Latin and in history classes.

But we must not forget that these stories about ancient history are also to be understood as documents of recent history: The stories which are told and the figures that are drawn do not only illustrate the ancient Gallic and Roman world, but also what was known and thought of it at the moment of their creation in the second half of the 20th century, due to the state of research and inextricably linked to the Zeitgeist.

As it has already been highlighted, all characters are stereotyped representatives for entire cultures. On the basis of stereotypes, racist and colonial elements can be found in the texts and images as well as anti-fascist, anti-imperial and anti-colonial elements. The aim of the lecture is to analyse which elements from ancient and which from other sources were processed, and how these various elements are combined in creating such stereotypic characters like Epidemais, the Phoenician.